

The Influence of Budget Targets, Human Resource Competence and Internal Control Government on the Quality of Government Agency Performance Reports (LKIP) with Commitment Organization as Moderating Variables at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the effect of clarity on budget targets, human resource competency, government internal control, organizational commitment, and analyze the ability of organizational commitment to moderate the relationship between clarity of budget targets, human resource competence, and government internal control with the quality of government agency performance reports. (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways. The sample of this research is 60 respondents. The population taken is an employee of the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways with a judgment (basic consideration), that these employees have gained experience in preparing LKIP.

The method of determining the sample using the saturated sample method and collecting data using a questionnaire and sampling used using non-probability sampling with a judgment sampling technique, this was done because the questionnaire period was carried out using an online survey with consideration of time and cost efficiency. Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis (multiple regression analysis). Data management will be carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) software application tool.

Based on the results of this study indicate that the first hypothesis budget targets have a negative effect on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP), it is concluded that a decrease in budget targets will cause a decrease in the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). The second hypothesis results that the human resource competencies contained in this study have a major influence on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP), because employees who have abilities in their fields can complete the job well, so that will have implications for improving the quality of performance reports for central government agencies resulting from. The third hypothesis

results that government internal control has a positive effect on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP), this indicates that changes that occur in the government internal control ratio will have a positive and significant effect on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). The fourth hypothesis, the organizational commitment of employees contained in this study has a major influence on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP), these results prove that the higher the organizational commitment of an employee, the performance will increase. The fifth hypothesis, organizational commitment weakens the influence of budget targets on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) but significantly in other words organizational commitment has no effect on the relationship between budget targets and the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). The sixth hypothesis, organizational commitment does not play a good enough role in moderating the relationship between human resource competency variables on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). The seventh hypothesis, organizational commitment does not play a good enough role in moderating the relationship between government internal control variables on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP).

Keywords:- Budget Target, Human Resource Competency, Government Internal Control, Quality Of Government Agency Performance Report (LKIP), And Organizational Commitment.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the concept of good governance, the government's role is to provide services for the welfare of the people with a good justice system and an accountable government system. To realize good governance, it is necessary to optimize the application of the principles of good governance which aims to improve government performance and create quality public services.

Government Agency Performance Reports (LKIP) are a form of accountability for each government agency in realizing good governance and clean government as stipulated in Presidential Regulation Number 29 of 2014 concerning Government Agency Performance Accountability Systems (SAKIP). The preparation of a performance accountability report is the obligation of a government agency to account for the success/failure of the implementation of programs and activities that have been mandated by stakeholders in order to achieve the organizational mission in a measurable manner with performance targets/targets that have been set through periodic, written government agency performance reports, and institutionalized.

The purpose of preparing LKIP is to inform and communicate the performance that has been achieved. As a form of communication media, LKIP is compiled systematically and periodically at the end of the current fiscal year in accordance with the Minister of Transportation PM Regulation Number 85 of 2020 concerning Guidelines for Implementing the Performance Accountability System of Government Agencies within the Ministry of Transportation with reference to Permenpan No. 53 of 2014 concerning Technical Guidelines for Performance Agreements, Performance Reporting and Procedures for Reviewing Government Agency Performance Reports and PAN-RB Ministerial Regulation Number 88 of 2021 concerning Evaluation of Government Agency Performance Accountability. The report used provides an overview of the assessment of the level of target achievement for each strategic target indicator set out in the 2020-2024 Road Transport and Railways Research and Development Center Strategic Plan document.

This system will measure and assess government performance based on the level of its ability to provide public services and the extent to which the public benefits from the services that must be provided by the central government. The increasing complexity of services has an impact on further implications for demands for increased performance and accountability for various policies/programs/activities carried out by the central government.

According to Yulia Yustikasari in the January 2022 MONEX Journal at Mercu Buana University, if the ability of village officials to manage village funds does not affect accountability in managing village funds, village government commitment affects accountability in managing village funds, and compliance with laws without affecting accountability of managing village funds. While the results of the study (Windi Pratiwi, 2020), LAKIP has a positive and significant influence on BPSDM Performance Improvement, based on the results of the partial test (t test) it has a tcount >

ttable where $3.625 > 1.99$ with a significance level of $0.001 < 0.025$ so it can be stated that the Government Agency Performance Accountability Report influences Performance Improvement. Based on the Adjusted R Square value of 0.144 or 14.4%, this indicates that the Performance Improvement variable can be explained by the government agency performance accountability report variable, while the remaining 85.6% is explained by other factors not included in this research model.

From several studies, organizational commitment has an effect on performance, so this variable is used as a moderation. According to research (Riyanto, 2022) with the results of the tcount hypothesis test showing 3.280 or > from t table 1.679 which means that organizational commitment partially affects managerial performance through budget participation. And organizational commitment partially affects managerial performance. This research is in line with the opinion that increasing budgetary participation will improve managerial performance, for organizational commitment partially affects managerial performance. Organizational commitment according to Sirin et al., (2020) is an individual's attachment to the organization, so that the individual feels a sense of belonging and tries to achieve organizational goals.

Even though it already has a performance measurement system and every year the government prepares LKIP, the information contained in the report has not been widely used in the decision-making process, because it turns out that government agencies do not have quality data like the phenomena that occur in the Road Transportation and Railway Research and Development Center, namely:

- Competence of human resources who have not been able to carry out an analysis of the success and failure of performance achievements and the proposed human resources are lacking and not ready, so that the proposed human resources do not match the expected qualifications;
- The government's internal control checks the 5 M (Mean, Material, Money and Method) for supporting data that is not completely available so that performance reports are not accompanied by supporting data attachments;
- Budget targets, in the preparation of performance agreements there was a mistake in placing the budget for monitoring activities in the current year, but instead it was allocated for monitoring activities for the use of research results, even though in practice monitoring activities for performance reports used SAKIP budget allocations so that in collecting data to support the preparation of performance reports such as financial statements have not yet been prepared.

In this study, the analytical tool to be used is Moderate Regression Analysis to find out the relationship that exists between each variable that is thought to affect employee performance, namely budget targets, human resource competence and government internal control as independent variables. as well as organizational commitment as a moderating variable that can strengthen or weaken the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The reason for using a moderating variable is that

there is a relationship between budget targets, human resource competence and government internal control on the increased quality of LKIP. Organizational commitment was chosen as a moderating variable because organizational commitment is considered to influence performance and ability to be responsible for the work entrusted. Organizational commitment is very important in its influence on work in order to create conducive working conditions so that the organization can run effectively and efficiently.

Based on the description of the background, phenomena and differences from the results of the research above on government agency performance accountability, the proposed research title is The Effect of Budget Targets, Human Resource Competence, and Government Internal Control on the Quality of Government Agency Performance Reports (LKIP) With Organizational Commitment As Moderating Variables at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.

In study this tool analysis to be used is moderation regression analysis (*Moderate Regression Analysis*) to find out the form of the relationship that occurs between each variable that is thought to affect employee performance, namely budget targets, human resource competence and government internal control as independent variables and organizational commitment as a moderating variable that can strengthen or weaken the relationship between independent variables and dependent. The reason for using a moderating variable is that there is a relationship between budget targets, human resource competence and government internal control on the increased quality of LKIP. Organizational commitment was chosen as a moderating variable because organizational commitment is considered to influence performance and ability to be responsible for the work entrusted. Organizational commitment is very important in its influence on work in order to create conducive working conditions so that the organization can run effectively and efficiently.

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A. Theory Contingencies

Harsh (2017) explained study based on contingency That require "hypothesis connection more from One variable independent with dependent".

B. Theory institutional

Institutional Theory (Institutional Theory) or institutional theory, namely the formation of organizations due to pressure from the institutional environment that causes institutionalization.

Based on institutional theory, organizations are formed based on forces from outside the organization through the process of compliance, imitation, and cognition (Dimaggio &

Powell, 2000). Institutional theory recognizes that organizations operate in a social sphere so that they will consider more social influences than pure economic influences (Musimenta et al., 2017).

In relation to the preparation and publication of public sector annual reports, the preparers of the annual reports on the performance of government agencies within the Ministries/Institutions are actually in the same regulatory environment. However, the practice of preparing and publishing this annual report then becomes different because each actor has a different logic that is influenced by the classification, routines and schemes within the respective K/L environment.

C. Target Budget

In organization sector public, budget is instrument accountability on management of public funds and implementation of the programs financed with public money. Budget sector public can said as something a financial plan that includes information among others:

- How much funds are needed to be spent to achieve the plans that have been prepared (expenditures/expenses);
- How much and how to obtain the funds needed to fund the plan drawn up (income).

D. Competence Source Power Man

Sedarmayanti (2017) explained that HR competencies are competencies that must be owned by someone to be able to occupy a certain position. In order to be able to occupy certain positions where there are job competency requirements, individuals must have the competencies according to the requirements so that there is a match between job competencies and individual competencies. The more in line with the competency standards of a particular position, the more successful a person will be in that position. To find out to what extent a person has a certain level of competence, then a person is eligible to occupy a certain position/position, measurement is carried out using the assessment center method, or Competency Based Interview (competence-based behavioral interview).

E. Government Internal Control

In the context of government administration, through Government Regulation Number 60 of 2008 the government stipulates the existence of an internal control system that must be implemented, both at the central and regional government levels. The intended internal control system is a process that is integral to the actions and activities carried out continuously by the leadership and all employees to provide adequate assurance of achieving organizational goals through effective and efficient activities, reliability of financial reporting, safeguarding state assets, and compliance with regulations. legislation. The internal control system is useful for controlling government activities in order to achieve effective, efficient, transparent and accountable state financial management

Based on the quotation above, it can be seen that internal control cannot eliminate all the problems faced by the company. Internal control has fundamental limitations, so that internal control only functions to find out problems

quickly and suppress problems and frauds that occur as low as possible.

F. Quality Agency Performance Report Government

The process of recording and measuring the achievement of the implementation of activities in the direction of achieving the mission (mission accomplishment) through the results displayed in the form of products, services or a process. Performance measurement is useful for assessing the results of implementing performance agreements according to the performance plan for the current year. Performance data is managed with the principle of accountability, namely transparency as the main requirement (Purnomo and Hafidz, 2018). Evaluation of government agency performance reports aims to find out the actual achievements, progress and obstacles encountered in the context of achieving the mission, so that they can be assessed and studied in order to improve the implementation of programs/activities in the future.

G. Commitment Organization

Organizational commitment is an attachment According to (Wiener, 1982) in Ferdinand et.,al (2020) organizational

H. Hypothesis

Fig. 1: Theoretical Framework

Based on from picture framework Based on the conceptual framework picture above, an alternative hypothesis is proposed from this study as follows:

- H1 : Budget targets affect the quality of LKIP at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.
- H2 : Human resource competence influences the quality of LKIP at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.
- H3 : Government internal control affects the quality of LKIP at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.
- H4 : Organizational Commitment influ-ences the quality of LKIP at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.

commitment is an encouragement from within the individual to do something so that it can support the success of the organization in accordance with its goals and prioritize the interests of the organization. There are two dominant concepts regarding organizational commitment according to Muthuvello and Rose (2005) cited in Yateno (2020). First, organizational commitment is a psychological condition for connecting employee relations with the organization. Second, organizational commitment has implications for employee decisions to continue or quit organizational membership. Broadly speaking, the types of public sector organizations can be divided into 3 (three), namely government agencies, government-owned non-profit organizations, and private-owned non-profit organizations.

Based on the above understanding, the identification in question is the identification of values, rules, and organizational goals carried out by employees.

- H5 : Organizational commitment is able to moderate the relationship between the clarity of budget targets and the quality of LKIP at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.
- H6 : Organizational commitment is able to moderate the relationship between HR competency and LKIP quality at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.
- H7 : Organizational commitment is able to moderate the relationship between government internal control and the quality of LKIP at the Center for Research and Development of Road Transportation and Railways.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The population in this study were 60 officials and employees at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways. The population taken is an employee of the Research and Development Center for Road

Transportation and Railways with a judgment (basic consideration), that these employees have gained experience in preparing LKIP.

Summary of *roles of thumbs* construct reliability test can be seen in the table below:

Table 1: Summary of roles of thumbs construct reliability test

Validitas dan Reliabilitas	Parameter	Rule Of Thumb
Validitas Convergent	<i>Loading Factor</i>	> 0.70 untuk <i>confirmatory Research</i> > 0.60 masih dapat diterima untuk <i>exploratory Research</i>
	<i>Average Variance Extracted (AVE)</i>	> 0.50 untuk <i>confirmatory</i> maupun <i>Exploratory Research</i>
Validitas Discriminant	<i>Cross Loading</i>	> 0.70 untuk setiap variabel
	Akar kuadrat AVE dan Korelasi antar konstruk laten	Akar kuadrat AVE > korelasi antar konstruk laten
Reliabilitas	<i>Cronbath's Alpha</i>	> 0.70 untuk <i>confirmatory Research</i> > 0.60 masih dapat diterima untuk <i>exploratory Research</i>
	<i>Composite Reliability</i>	> 0.70 untuk <i>confirmatory Research</i> > 0.60 – 0.70 masih dapat diterima untuk <i>exploratory Research</i>

Table 2: Summary Return Questionnaire

No	Information	Amount
1.	Head of Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways	1
2.	Commitment Making Officer (PPK)	1
3.	Head Field (Development Technology Support Research, Program and Evaluation)	2
4.	Head of Sub Division	5
5.	Manager Budget and Finance	10
6.	LKIP Preparation Team	3
7.	Employee	38
Amount returned questionnaire _		60
The questionnaire used in study		60
Rate of return (<i>response rate</i>) (60/60 x 100%)		100%

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data collection was carried out by direct distribution through online surveys to respondents. For this study, a total of 25 questions were asked in this questionnaire. The questionnaire was then distributed from January to April 2023. The proportion of respondents based on those obtained during the distribution of the sex questionnaire was divided into 2 categories where men and women totaled 36 men and 24 women.

of 60%, while female respondents were 24 with a percentage of 40%.

Table 3: Characteristics Based on Gender

Gender	Amount	Percentage
Man	36	60%
Woman	24	40%
Amount	60	100%

Table 1 shows that the highest frequency of respondents in this study was male with 36 respondents and a percentage

Table 4: Characteristics Based on Age

Age	Amount	Percentage
<25 Years	3	5%
26 – 35 Years	23	38.3%
36 – 50 Years	32	53.3%
>50 Years	2	3.33%
Amount	60	100%

4.2 above it can be seen that the highest frequency based on age is respondents with an age range of <25 years with a total of 3 respondents and a percentage of 5%, while respondents with an age range of 26-35 years are 23 respondents with a percentage of 38.3%, respondents with a range of There were 32 respondents aged 36-50 years with a percentage of 53.3% and respondents with an age range of >50 years were 2 respondents with a percentage of 3.33%.

Table 5: Characteristics Respondents

Education	Amount	Percentage
SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	0	0%
D3	2	3.3%
S1/D4	38	63.3%
S2	20	33.3%
S3	0	0%
Amount	60	100%

Based on Education In table 4 it can be seen that the last education of high school respondents is 0 people or 0%, D3 is 2 people or 3.3%, S1/D4 is 38 people or 63.3%, S2 is 20 people or 33.3%, and S3 there are 0 people or 0%. This happened because most of the respondents had the last education level S1/D4.

Table 6: Characteristics Respondents Based on Working Period

Working Period	Amount	Percentage
<1 Year	0	0%
1-3 Years	17	28.3%
3-5 Years	14	23.3%
>5 Years	29	48.3%
Amount	60	100%

In table 4.4 it can be seen that respondents based on years of service, namely <1 year there were 0 people or 0%, 1-3 years there were 17 people or 28.3%, 3-5 years there were 14 people or 23.3%, and > 5 years there are 29 people or 48.3%. This happened because most of the respondents had a working period of >5 years.

A. Reliability Test

A variable is said to meet construct reliability if it has a composite reliability value of > 0.7 (Billy J. Maspaitella et al, 2018) and a cronbach alpha value of > 0.7 has a good level of reliability for a variable (Assegaff, 2015). Composite reliability value of each reliability indicator.

Table 6: Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite reliability	Information
Target Budget (X1)	0.946	0.959	reliable
Competence Source Power Human (X2)	0.826	0.877	reliable
Government Internal Control (X3)	0.892	0.921	reliable
Quality Agency Performance Report Government (Y)	0.848	0.891	reliable
Commitment Organization (Z)	0.806	0.863	reliable

Reliability can explained that is variable target budget with *Cronbach's Alpha* of 0.946 and *composite reliability* of 0.959 then declared reliable, variable competence source Power man with *Cronbach's Alpha* of 0.826 and *composite reliability* of 0.877 then declared reliable, variable government internal control with *Cronbach's Alpha* of 0.892 and *composite reliability* of 0.921 then declared reliable, variable quality report performance agency government with *Cronbach's Alpha* of 0.848 meanwhile *composite reliability* of 0.891 then declared reliable, and variable commitment organization with *Cronbach's Alpha* of 0.806 meanwhile *composite reliability* of 0.863 then declared reliable.

It can be seen from the results of the reliability test analysis using the SmartPLS tool which states that all composite reliability values are greater than 0.7, which means that all variables are reliable and meet the test criteria.

Furthermore, the cronbach's alpa value also shows that all cronbach's alpa values are more than 0.6 and this indicates the level of reliability of the variable also meets the criteria.

B. Validity Test

In this study, the measurement validity test consisted of convergent validity and discriminant validity.

➤ **Validity Convergent**

Convergent validity is used to measure the correlation between item scores and construct scores, the higher the correlation the better the validity of the data (Nur Ayu Setia Ningsih & Sigit Hermawan, 2019). Measurements can be categorized as having convergent validity if the loading factor value is > 0.7 (Ghaliyah Nimassipta Triseptya, Gagaring Pagulung & Aini Indrijawati, 2017).

Fig. 2: SmartPLS models _

Source: SmartPLS 3.0 output processed , 2023

Table 7 Loading factor Moderating With Organizational Commitment

Variable	Target Budget (X1)	Competence Source Power Human (X2)	Government Internal Control (X3)
Target Budget (X1)	2,525		
Competence Source Power Human (X2)		2,180	
Government Internal Control (X3)			2,313

Loading factor moderating with organizational commitment can be explained, namely the budget target variable of 2.525, the human resource competency variable of 2.180, and the government's internal control variable of 2.313. So it shows that all loading factors have a value > 0.7, so it can be concluded that all indicators have met the convergent validity criteria, because there are no indicators for all variables that have been eliminated from the model.

➤ *Validity Distribution*

Validity one of the discriminants can be seen with compare AVE value with correlation between construct other in models. If value root AVE > 0.50, then It means validity discriminant reached (Novrian Dandi Pratama, Ahim Abdulrahim & Hafiez Sofyan, 2018).

Table 8: AVE Value

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Target Budget (X1)	0.825
Competence Source Power Human (X2)	0.589
Government Internal Control (X3)	0.701
Quality Agency Performance Report Government (Y)	0.621
Commitment Organization (Z)	0.558

The AVE value for the budget target variable is 0.825, human resource competency is 0.589, government internal control is 0.701, the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) is 0.621, and organizational

commitment is 0.558 with a value > 0.50. So it can be said that the measurement model has discriminant validity.

Besides that is, validity discrimination is also carried out based on measurement *fornell larcker criterion* with construct.

Table 9: Fornell Larcker Criterions

Variable	Commitment Organization (Z)	Competence Source Power Human (X2)	Quality Agency Performance Report Government (Y)	Government Internal Control (X3)	Target Budget (X1)
Z	0.747				
X2	0.709	0.768			
Y	0.797	0.850	0.788		
X3	0.679	0.757	0.829	0.837	
X1	0.670	0.787	0.777	0.881	0.908

The Fornell Larcker criterion can be explained with the highest value with the budget target variable of 0.908, the human resource competency variable of 0.768, the government's internal control variable of 0.837, the variable quality of government agency performance reports of 0.788, and the organizational commitment variable of 0.747.

Based on the table above it appears that each statement indicator has the highest loading factor value on the latent construct tested than the other latent constructs, meaning that each statement indicator is able to predict well by each latent construct, in other words, discriminant validity is valid. So it

can be concluded from the results of table 4.8. and 4.9. all constructs met the criteria of discriminant validity.

➤ *Structural Model (Inner Model)*

R-Square values 0.75, 0.50 and 0.25 can concluded that the model is strong, moderate and weak (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). The criteria are:

- If the value of R2 = 0.75 then substantial (big / strong)
- If the value of R2 = 0.50 then moderate (medium)
- If the value of R2 = 0.25 then weak (small)

C. Output R- Square adjusted

Square and R- Square values adjusted

Table 10: Square and R- Square values adjusted

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Quality Agency Performance Report agency Government (LKIP) (Y)	0.861	0.842

Adjusted R-Square Model is 0. 842, meaning that the ability of the dependent variable in explaining Y is 84.2% (big/strong), so it is said that the ability of the variable budget targets, human resource competence, and government internal control is strong, namely 84.2% , while the remaining 15.8% are other independent influences that are not regulated in this study.

D. Hypothesis Test

The next step is to test the hypotheses that have been built in this study. In this case, the bootstrapping method was

carried out on the sample. Testing with bootstrapping is intended to minimize the problem of abnormal research data.

The final step of the test using the smart-PLS application is a hypothesis test and is carried out by looking at the results of the bootstrapping value. This test is carried out by selecting the calculate menu and after that a menu option appears, then selecting bootstrapping, then the desired data will appear. Following are the results of the data test using bootstrapping.

Fig. 3: Bootstrapping. Test

Criteria mark *path coefficient* are :

- If the value positive , then influence something variable to the variable it influences is in the same direction . If value something variable exogenous increases /rises, then mark endogenous variables also increased up.
- If value *path coefficient* is negative , then influence something variable to variable other is opposite direction
- If value something variable exogenous rising up, then mark endogenous variables decreased .
- Hypothesis study can accepted If t count value (t-statistic) > t table at the level error (α) 5% is 1.96.
- Significance probability value (P-Value):
- If the P-Values <0.05, then it is significant;
- If the P-Values value is > 0.05, then it is not significant.

Tabel 11: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Connection	Path Coefficient	T-Statistics	P-Values	Results
H1	X1 →Y	-0.158	0.926	0.314	Rejected
H2	X2 →Y	0.414	2,677	0.008	Accepted
H3	X3 →Y	0.464	2,761	0.005	Accepted
H4	Z →Y	0.306	3,293	0.001	Accepted
H5	X1*Z →Y	-0.071	0.489	0.640	Rejected
H6	X2*Z →Y	0.259	1.618	0.106	Rejected
H7	X3*Z →Y	-0.161	0.954	0.367	Rejected

Based on table previously obtained information results testing hypothesis as following :

- The first hypothesis shows that the results of data processing show that H1 in this study is rejected. The results of this study indicate that there is no significant relationship between budget targets (X1) and LKIP quality (Y) which is negative. The direction of the relationship can be seen from the value of the Original Sample number in Bootstipping which is -158. In terms of significance, this relationship is not significant because the t-statistic value is 0.926 which means it is smaller than the t-table which is 1.65. In addition, the resulting research P-Value, which is 0.314, also exceeds the predetermined standard (<0.05). The interpretation of this finding is that if the budget target decreases, it will cause a decrease in the quality of the government agency performance report (LKIP). The implications of contingency theory in budget targets describe an effort to identify according to the control system under the right conditions, even though the budget targets have been made clear, errors in each individual are inevitable, because the individual does not have sufficient information to predict the future appropriately. Therefore the central government's budget targets must be clearly stated, specific, and understandable to those responsible for implementing them. This encourages employees/staff to do their best to achieve the desired goals so that it has implications for the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). This result is in line with previous research that was conducted by (Richard Arya Prakasa. 2020). This study found empirical evidence that the clarity of budgetary goals has no effect on budget gaps. This indicates that high or low clarity of budget targets will not affect the budget gap. Thus, the results of this study were rejected. And in line with the research conducted (Andi Mattulada Amir, Ridwan, Muhammad Din, Nina Yusra Yamin, Familia Zahra, and Muh. Fiqram Firman. 2021) which shows that participation budget has a positive effect on the performance of government apparatus, budget participation has a negative effect on budgetary slack and negative budgetary slack on the performance of government officials. While this research is in line with research conducted by (Abongile Goodman Zweni, Larry Enoch Jowah. 2018) which states that Budgeting is done by Executive management and passed down to managers to implement. It is expected that employees who are involved directly or indirectly with budgeting will have to at least be given input when budgets are formulated. The budget process should begin from the bottom (employees) of the organization to the top (senior management or senior politicians). If top management does not have gratitude or promotes interpersonal relationships between different levels of the hierarchy, it is likely to fail and to achieve its goals and objectives. Furthermore involving middle to lower management will not only motivate them but the budget process will give the ownership of the projects and allocations.
- The second hypothesis shows that the results of data processing show that H2 in this study is accepted. The results of this study indicate that there is a positive and significant relationship between human resource competence (X2) and the quality of LKIP. The direction of

the relationship can be seen from the Original Sample value of 0.414. Significance is shown by the t-statistic number of 2.677 which is greater than the t-table (1.65). The research P-Value value of 0.008 also meets predetermined standards, namely (<0.05). The interpretation of this finding is that the better the competence of human resources has a major influence on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP), because employees who have the ability in their fields can complete the job well, so that will have implications for improving the quality of the resulting central government agency performance reports. Through this contingency theory approach, the competence of human resources in each organization causes differences in characteristic needs for the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP).

The results of this study are in line with and in line with the results of previous studies from:

- ✓ Ramgopal K. Ratnawat. 2018. Mumbai (India), Competency based human resource management is a useful approach towards managing different aspects of employee management ranging from recruitment and selection to separation and succession planning. The method has distinct advantages in terms of more clarity of roles and responsibilities as well as the expected outcomes and the kind of attributes required to perform the given jobs effectively. When embedded into HR processes, competency-based management significantly improves their effectiveness as demonstrated through research quoted in this review. This article synthesizes the relevant knowledge and serves as a 'ready reckoner' for competency-based management and related concepts to further the knowledge in this area.;
- ✓ Ngurah, et al, (2017); Oktaviyanti, et al, (2017); Zubaidi, et al, (2019) which shows that human resource competency partially has a significant effect on the quality of financial reports with a significant value less than 0.01;
- ✓ Ferdius Azam S.M., Yusoff Mohd Khalidah Siti.2019. Malaysia, the results of the study show that the internal control system and human resource competency have a positive effect on the quality of local government financial report information. Internal control systems and human resource competencies also have a positive effect on financial accountability, both directly and indirectly, mediated by the quality of local government financial reporting information.
- The third hypothesis shows that the results of data processing show that H3 in this study is accepted. The results showed that the relationship between government internal control (X3) and LKIP quality (Y) was positive and significant. The direction of the relationship can be seen from the Original Sample value in Bootstipping of 0.464. Significance is shown by the t-statistical value of government internal control (X3) on LKIP quality (Y) of 0.2761 which is greater than t-table (1.65). In addition, the research P-Value is 0.005 which also meets the standard (<0.05). The interpretation of this finding is that the increasing number of benefits of government internal control will be followed by the growing confidence in the

quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). This supports the contingency theory of appropriate government internal control depending on the setting of central government agencies. The results of this study are aligned and relevant to the results of previous studies that have been conducted by:

- ✓ Wonder Agbenyo, Yuansheng Jiang & Price Komla Cobblah. 2018. University of Ghana, Legon. Based on the data obtained, and the findings set out, the researcher concludes that internal control plays an important role and has a positive impact on the quality of financial reporting especially when all parties are involved here for the purpose of managing public finances in Ghana;
- ✓ Swarmilah Daily. 2020. Malaysia, the results of the study are that the variable understanding of the principles of good governance and the internal control system has a significant positive effect on the performance of government agencies, while organizational commitment has no effect on the performance of government agencies;
- ✓ Oyetunji, O.T., Lawal, B.A., Yinus, S.O., Akodu, A.A., and Lawal, B.O. 2021, with the results of the analysis showing that internal control has a significant relationship with budget control.
- The fourth hypothesis shows that the results of data processing show that the H4 value in this study is accepted. The results of the research show that there is a positive and significant direct relationship between organizational commitment and the quality of LKIP. The direction of the relationship can be seen from the Original Sample value of 0.306. The significance of the research is indicated by the t-statistic number of 3.293 which means it is greater than the t-table (1.65). The research P-Value of 0.001 also met the predetermined standard (<0.05). The interpretation of this finding is that the more employee organizational commitment contained in this study has a major influence on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways. These results prove that the higher the organizational commitment of an employee, the performance will increase. So that institutional theory of organizational commitment will have a tendency to try to adjust to external expectations or social expectations where the organization is located. These results are relevant and in line with research conducted by:
 - ✓ Umpusinga, Afandi Hasrun. 2022. The results of the study concluded that hypothesis one was fulfilled, namely organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance;
 - ✓ Bora Ly. College of Graduate Studies, Walailak University, Thailand. January 2023, the effect of inclusive leadership (IL) on organizational commitment (AOC) was found to be significant and positive, confirming a direct link between IL and AOC in the context of Cambodian public organizations;
 - ✓ Sri Gustina Pane and Fatmawati. 2017, the results of the analysis show that affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment simultaneously (to-gether) have a significant effect on employee performance.
- The fifth hypothesis shows that the results of data processing show that H5 in this study was rejected. The research results show that there is a negative direct relationship between budget targets and the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) and organizational commitment. The direction of the relationship can be seen from the Original Sample value in Bootstrapping of -0.071. In terms of significance, this relationship is not significant because the t-statistic value is 0.489 which means it is smaller than the t-table which is 1.65. In addition, the P-Value was 0.625 which indicated that the significance of the study was rejected because it exceeded a predetermined standard (<0.05). Therefore, the research hypothesis was rejected. The interpretation of this finding is that the higher the budget target, the lower the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) and vice versa. Meanwhile, from an indirect relationship, organizational commitment (Z) does not have a mediating role in the relationship between budget targets and the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). Therefore, it can be concluded in this study using institutional theory that there is a possibility that organizational commitment to budget targets is not optimal so that it cannot affect the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways in the process of preparing government budgets. If the quality of government agency performance reports will run well if it is supported by strong organizational commitment, it will have a better chance of achieving the desired budget target results. The results of this study are not in line with the research conducted (Andi Mattulada Amir, Ridwan, Muhammad Din, Nina Yusnita Yamin, Femilia Zahra, and Muh. Fiqram Firman. 2021) The results of this study also show that budgetary slack is a partial mediator between the two effects of budget participation on the performance of local government apparatus. This result is in line with research previously conducted by Silta Aglisnema (2019), which stated that the organizational commitment variable has no influence on the relationship between clarity of budget targets and accountability for government agency performance. And the results in this study are relevant to the results obtained by previous research conducted by (Leny Irma Yanti and Heri Widodo. 2022), the results of the study show that there is no effect of organizational commitment in the relationship between budgetary participation and managerial performance in the GAPENSI company.
- The sixth hypothesis shows that the results of data processing show that H6 in this study was rejected. The results of the study show that there is a direct relationship between human resource competence on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) and organizational commitment is positive. The direction of the relationship can be seen from the Original Sample value in Bootstrapping of 0.259. In terms of significance, this relationship is not significant because the t-statistic value is 1.618 which means it is smaller than the t-table which is 1.65. In addition, the P-Value was 0.106 which indicated that the significance of the study was rejected because it exceeded a predetermined standard (<0.05). The

interpretation of this finding is that more and more human resource competencies are followed by organizational commitment to the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). Meanwhile, from an indirect relationship perspective, it appears that organizational commitment (Z) does not play a moderating role in the relationship between human resource competence (X3) and the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP). That organizational commitment does not play a good enough role in moderating the relationship between the variable competence of human resources which is an institutional theory which is the main driver of the operation of an organization, including if there is a change in the organization. The results of this study are institutional theories that explain organizational commitment resulting in organizational tendencies to separate internal activities and focus on systems that are symbolic to external parties, where a less than optimal organizational commitment in explaining budget targets so that it cannot affect the quality of government agencies' performance reports in decision making. So that the results of this study are included in institutional theory in which organizational commitment does not meet the expected human resource competency characteristics for the quality of government agency performance reports.

- The results in this study are not relevant to the results obtained by previous research conducted by Raharjo, K., Nurjannah, N., Solimun, S. And Achmad Rinaldo Fernandes, A. (2018), with the results of the influence of organizational culture and work commitment on human resource performance is also significant. In addition, the mediating effect of the Work Commitment variable was found on the influence of Job Design and Organizational Culture on Human Resource Performance. While the results of this study are in line with previous research conducted by Ardyan Firdausi Mustofa, Nur Sayidatul Muntiah, Fitria Dwi Susanti. 2021, with the results of research on organizational commitment not being able to moderate village government competence and accountability.
- The seventh hypothesis shows that the results of data processing show that the H7 value in this study is rejected. The direction of the relationship can be seen from the Original Sample value in Bootstrapping of -0.161. In terms of significance, this relationship is not significant because the t-statistic value is 0.954 which means it is smaller than the t-table which is 1.65. In addition, the P-Value was 0.341 which indicated that the significance of the study was rejected because it exceeded a predetermined standard (<0.05). The interpretation that can be made is that the higher the government's internal control, the lower the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways and vice versa. Meanwhile, from an indirect relationship, organizational commitment (Z) does not have a mediating role in the relationship between government internal control. In addition, this study provides conclusions from institutional theory that organizational commitment does not play a good enough role in moderating the relationship between government

internal control variables on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP).

The results in this study are not relevant to the results obtained by previous studies conducted by:

- Marus Eton (Kabale University and Fabian Mwosi (Bishop Barham University College). March 2022, with specific results, control environment and control monitoring have a significant effect on financial accountability while control activities do not.
- Ardyan Firdausi Mustofa, Nur Sayidatul Muntiah, Fitria Dwi Susanti. 2021, with the results of research on organizational commitment moderating the relationship between the internal control system and village government accountability and strengthening the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the formulation of the problem and the hypothesis proposed, as well as the results of research based on the results of both descriptive and statistical analysis with employees, the conclusions put forward in this study can be drawn as follows:

- Budget targets do not have an important influence on improving the quality of government agency performance reports on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.
- There is a significant influence on the competence of human resources which affects the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways. This illustrates the competency of human resources having the ability to make good reports at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways.
- There is a significant influence in the government's internal control on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP), so that policies and procedures for physical security of assets have been established and implemented effectively, efficiently, and can be managed properly. So that the more developed the government's internal control, the better the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP).
- Organizational commitment affects the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways, because the higher the organizational commitment, the higher the responsibility entrusted, the higher the responsibility will have an impact on the performance carried out by employees.
- Organizational commitment does not strengthen the relationship between budget target variables on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways. Organizational commitment in the central government may still be suboptimal in setting clear and specific budget targets.

- Organizational commitment does not play a good enough role in moderating the relationship between human resource competence variables on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways because the number of human resources is limited and some do not understand the procedure for preparing performance reports so that performance reports are not timely and less accountable.
- Organizational commitment does not play a good enough role in moderating the relationship between government internal control variables on the quality of government agency performance reports (LKIP) at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways because the Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) that exist in entities do not run optimally and supporting data for government internal control has not yet been completed from other sub-sectors/sections in checking the 5 M (Mean, Material, Money and Method) not fully available.

Suggestions that the author wants to give so that further research can be better, namely:

- The quality of government agency performance reports at the Research and Development Center for Road Transportation and Railways requires data support from other sections, so that the active role and participation of other sections is expected in providing data to support performance reporting. Performance reporting can be monitored through the WhatsApp group as a means of communication.
- It is necessary to develop human resource competencies (HR) to overcome some of the obstacles that occur in the preparation of LKIP in order to obtain more optimal results, such as forming a team to compile LKIP, improving coordination of sub-sectors, and conducting training.
- Performance measurement should be carried out at each stage of activity to find out how far the performance has been achieved at a certain time, so that a plan can be drawn up to achieve targets in accordance with the timeline that has been prepared.
- Planning needs to be made in detail by compiling a timeline for the implementation of the activity plan so that it can end on time and not pile up at the end of the year.

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